

Synthesis and Characterization of *p*-Hydroxybenzoic Acid-Thiourea-Trioxane Copolymers

M. M. PATEL* and R. MANAVAN

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

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Copolymers were synthesized by the condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (PHB) and thiourea (T) with trioxane (T') in the presence of HCl (2*M*) as catalyst and varying molar proportions of the reactants. Copolymer prepared from equimolar proportions of reactants was fractionated. The polymer samples were characterized by ir spectra, \bar{M}_n determined by vapour pressure osmometry as well as by non-aqueous conductometric titrations, elemental analysis and TGA. Viscosity measurements of the solutions of polymer samples were carried out in dimethylformamide. Electrical property of polymer PHBTT'-1 has been studied. Chelation and ion exchanging properties of the polymers PHBTT'-1 and PHBTT'-2 were also studied by employing the batch equilibrium method.

ALTHOUGH in recent years there has been considerable interest shown in sulphur and selenium containing ligands¹⁻³, the former have been less extensively studied. Dithiocarbamates have attracted the attention on account of their wide ranging biological activities⁴. 1,3,4-Thiadiazole nucleus and its derivatives have received much attention as potential bactericides, fungicides, insecticides, herbicides and flower control agents⁵. Condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid with formaldehyde in presence of oxalic or hydrochloric acid afforded a polymer⁶. The molecular mass of condensate and the fractions separated was estimated conductometrically in non-aqueous media⁷. The effects of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid formaldehyde condensate on virus and blood cells have been reported⁸.

Keeping in view the varied activities of sulphur containing compounds and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid-formaldehyde polymers, *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid-thiourea-trioxane (PHBTT') copolymers have been prepared by condensing *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and thiourea with trioxane in presence of HCl (2*M*) as catalyst.

Experimental

All the reagents were of high purity. DMF (E. Merck) was dehydrated by keeping over anhydrous sodium carbonate for one day, decanted and then distilled. All the monomers (B. D. H., AnalaR) were used without further purification.

Preparation of the copolymers: A mixture of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and thiourea (0.1 mol each) and trioxane (0.2 mol) in the presence of 2*M* HCl was heated in an oil bath at $130 \pm 2^\circ$ for 4 h. The yellow coloured polymer obtained was washed with hot water and finally with ether to remove excess of

acid monomer. The product was purified by dissolving in aqueous NaOH (10%) and reprecipitated with HCl (1:1). The copolymer thus obtained was washed with boiling water and dried.

The fractional precipitation method was employed for fractionating copolymer sample PHBTT'-1 (Table 1). DMF was used as the solvent and HCl (1:1) as precipitant. A 3% solution of polymer sample was prepared and filtered through G₃ sintered glass funnel. The non-solvent mixture was added dropwise with stirring to the solution until a moderately strong opalescence. The solution was then warmed till the opalescence completely disappeared. The solution was allowed to cool to attain thermal equilibrium ($30 \pm 0.1^\circ$) with continuous stirring and was left overnight in the thermostat whereby the precipitate agglomerated and settled. The supernatant liquid was siphoned off and the settled polymer in the form of film was dried. A series of fractions, PHBTT'-1a, PHBTT'-1b, PHBTT'-1c and PHBTT'-1d, (Table 1) of regularly decreasing molecular weight were collected similarly.

Analytical methods and physical measurements: Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl method and sulphur as BaSO₄ by the Carius method. The conductivity of the polymer samples in pyridine was measured by the reported method⁹ using a Konduktoskop Metrohm Harisau conductometer. Number average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) of all the polymers was estimated by vapor pressure osmometry method using DMF as solvent and benzil as calibrant.

Viscometric measurements of the solutions of the polymer samples were carried out using an Ubbelohde viscometer at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. IR spectra were recorded in KBr with a UR-10 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetry analysis of all the polymer

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION OF COPOLYMERS

Sl. No. PHBTT'	Mole ratio PHB : T : T'	Yield %	Conductometric titration of copolymer (in pyridine against TBH base)				Copolymer composition by sulphur content
			mmol of base added at first break (X)	mmol of base added at final break (Y)	$\bar{D}l = Y/X$	\bar{M}_n	
1	1 : 1 : 2	75.5	85	410	4.8	1121	0.45 : 0.37
1a	Fraction-I	15.0	115	495	5.4	1315	0.451 : 0.367
1b	Fraction-II	12.5	105	550	5.3	1245	0.46 : 0.35
1c	Fraction-III	10.5	105	495	4.7	1130	0.456 : 0.358
1d	Fraction-IV	10.0	90	390	4.3	1025	0.45 : 0.366
2	3 : 1 : 4	45.0	100	435	4.4	965	0.575 : 0.156
3	1 : 3 : 4	72.0	110	385	3.6	815	0.258 : 0.695
4	5 : 1 : 6	73.0	125	505	4.2	942	0.61 : 0.093

TABLE 2—CHARACTERIZATION OF COPOLYMERS

Copolymer sample	Conductometric titration of copolymers				$\bar{D}P = C/D$	\bar{M}_n	Copolymer composition	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		$[\eta] \times 10^4$ dl g ⁻¹	$\nu_{C=S}$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm ⁻¹
	Total COOH + OH groups (titration against NaOMe base) mmol (A)	Total COOH groups (titration against TBAH base) mmol (B)	Total OH groups mmol A-B=C	NaOMe base added at first break of titration curve mmol (D)				N	S			
PHBTT'-1	870	410	460	90	5.1	822	0.45 : 0.39	11.23 (11.76)	11.88 (12.41)	6.52	860	1650
PHBTT'-1a	910	495	415	110	3.7	885	0.46 : 0.38	10.98 (11.76)	11.75 (12.41)	10.83	850	1648
PHBTT'-1b	925	550	375	115	3.3	731	0.45 : 0.41	11.36 (11.76)	11.06 (12.41)	7.21	856	1650
PHBTT'-1c	950	495	455	105	4.3	713	0.44 : 0.42	11.02 (11.76)	11.48 (12.41)	6.75	856	1648
PHBTT'-1d	880	390	490	95	5.1	686	0.41 : 0.38	10.89 (11.76)	11.72 (12.41)	6.31	852	1650
PHBTT'-2	950	435	515	110	4.7	747	0.58 : 0.17	4.29 (5.21)	5.01 (5.94)	5.69	852	1645
PHBTT'-3	1025	385	640	125	5.1	671	0.24 : 0.71	20.74 (20.28)	22.27 (23.18)	4.85	860	1648
PHBTT'-4	975	505	270	90	3.0	708	0.64 : 0.085	2.45 (3.34)	2.98 (3.82)	5.11	856	1650

samples was carried out on a Du Pont-950 thermogravimetric analyzer in CO₂ atmosphere at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹.

The batch equilibrium method was adopted for the ion exchanging properties^{9,10}. The evaluation of the influence of different electrolytes on the metal uptake by the polymer, the rate of metal uptake under specified conditions and the distribution of various metal ions at different pH values were carried out following the details of the procedures described earlier¹¹.

Results and Discussion

The probable structure of the copolymers have been determined on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data. Copolymer samples were in powder form having pale yellow colour and were soluble both in pyridine and DMF. Exact melting points of these samples could not be found out as they started softening at 175°. The composition of the monomers in the polymer samples has been

calculated from both conductometric titrations and sulphur estimation and was found to be comparable. The examination of the molecular weights of all polymer samples (Table 1) reveals that the values of each copolymer sample estimated by the conductometric titration method and by the VPO method are comparable within limits of experimental error. The polymer sample obtained using equimolar proportion of the two monomers (PHB and T) has the highest molecular weight in the series.

The viscometric measurements in DMF were obtained and plots of reduced viscosity vs concentration (3.0 to 1.152 g dl⁻¹) were made for each set of data. The intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta]$ was determined from the corresponding linear plots (Table 2). It has been observed that the copolymers and fractions having higher \bar{M}_n show higher values of $[\eta]$. It is also noted that the intrinsic viscosity of polymer samples obtained in presence of greater quantity of catalyst is usually higher¹².

The ir spectra of the copolymers reveal broad resemblance. However, certain small but definite

TABLE 3—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF COPOLYMERS

Copolymer no.	Percentage weight loss at different temp. in air, °C						Decom. temp. °C	Order of reaction temp. range		Energy of activation k cal mol ⁻¹	
	100	200	300	400	500	600		700	n=1		n=2
1	2.0	5.5	20.0	38.0	55.0	81.0	85.0	245	500-700	40-200	5.01
1a	1.0	4.0	30.0	47.0	58.0	80.0	89.5	250	250-650	40-200	4.28
1b	3.0	6.0	31.0	48.0	65.0	87.0	90.0	235	260-600	40-220	4.25
1c	2.0	4.0	31.0	48.0	54.0	65.0	77.0	215	220-640	40-200	4.88
1d	2.0	6.0	36.0	45.0	56.0	75.0	77.0	225	300-600	40-250	3.75
2	3.0*	5.0	25.0	45.0	55.0	76.0	80.0	250	350-600	40-220	3.21
3	2.0	8.0	25.0	51.0	60.0	85.0	85.0	245	350-650	40-350	4.01
4	2.0	6.0	35.0	42.0	55.0	80.0	86.0	220	300-600	60-300	2.99

points of difference are observed. The spectra show a band at 2800-3050 cm⁻¹ ascribed to aromatic C-H stretching and methylene groups¹³. 1400-1500 cm⁻¹ represents methylene bending (scissoring) modes which afford clear evidence for the existence of a number of methylene groups in the copolymers. This is further evident from the bands appearing in the range of 1250-1350 cm⁻¹ due to methylene bending (twisting and wagging) modes. A sharp band at ~1650 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C=O stretching vibrations in COOH group. The spectra also show strong bands at 2900-3350 cm⁻¹ (NH), 1600-1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N stretch)¹⁴ and at 850-860 cm⁻¹ (C=S)¹⁵. A weak band observed in the region 2380-2420 cm⁻¹ (SH) indicates that the copolymers may exist in equilibrium in the keto and enol tautomeric forms¹⁶.

The examination of the results of TGA (Table 3) reveals that each polymer sample undergoes degradation in two steps like salicylic acid-formaldehyde polymer¹⁷, the first stage being attributed to decarboxylation. In the present cases the first stage terminates in the region from 240-300° with the material loss around 40% of its weight depending on the nature of the polymer. It was further noted that decomposition began slowly at ~245° and became rapid at ~300°. It seems that the reaction was complete at ~600° and resulted in 80 to 90% loss in sample weight. These results show that among the polymer samples prepared in presence of the same catalyst but with different molar proportions of the reactants, the one prepared with equimolar proportions of the reactants is more stable. The first step in the thermal degradation of the copolymers may be due to the decarboxylation and further degradation in the second step may be a random degradation reaction affording simpler degradation products¹⁸. The kinetic parameters have also been calculated¹⁹ and furnished in Table 3. It is very difficult to draw any conclusion from the magnitude of thermal activation energy as the decomposition mechanism is expected to be very much complicated²⁰.

Ion-exchanging properties: The results of the batch equilibrium study carried out with polymer samples PHBTI'-1 and PHBTI'-2 are presented in Tables 4, 5 and 6. The examination of the data given in Table 4 reveals that the amount of metal

TABLE 4—EVALUATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES IN THE UPTAKE OF SEVERAL METAL (M) IONS †

Metal ion	Electrolyte mol. dm ⁻¹	Weight in mg × 10 of the metal ion taken up* in the presence of			
		NaClO ₄	NaCl	NaNO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₄
Cu ²⁺	0.01	1.6 (2.12)	1.01 (2.12)	1.17 (1.06)	3.15 (4.43)
	0.05	1.9 (2.50)	2.09 (3.11)	1.63 (2.01)	2.42 (2.98)
	0.10	2.31 (3.12)	2.19 (2.98)	2.05 (2.61)	1.64 (1.61)
	0.50	2.75 (4.01)	3.05 (3.75)	2.43 (3.76)	0.98 (1.11)
	1.00	3.36 (4.62)	3.34 (4.19)	2.56 (3.46)	0.37 (0.31)
Fe ³⁺	0.01	0.98 (1.12)	0.26 (0.31)	0.86 (1.12)	2.22 (2.52)
	0.05	1.42 (1.88)	0.75 (0.88)	1.25 (1.42)	1.31 (1.22)
	0.10	2.12 (1.97)	1.23 (1.79)	1.68 (1.89)	1.28 (1.41)
	0.50	2.31 (2.63)	1.87 (2.43)	1.87 (2.22)	0.63 (0.98)
	1.00	2.95 (3.33)	2.54 (3.05)	2.31 (2.69)	0.21 (0.43)
UO ₂ ⁺	0.01	1.95 (2.12)	1.14 (1.39)	1.08 (1.39)	5.43 (5.69)
	0.05	2.61 (2.83)	1.07 (1.76)	1.69 (2.16)	4.81 (5.32)
	0.10	3.84 (3.96)	1.63 (1.92)	2.19 (2.42)	4.37 (5.01)
	0.50	4.32 (5.41)	2.14 (2.63)	4.83 (4.99)	3.20 (3.79)
	1.00	5.42 (6.33)	2.29 (3.23)	5.02 (5.33)	2.50 (3.11)

† [M(NO₃)₂] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³; Volume of electrolyte solution = 25 ml; metal solution = 2 ml.

* Figures are for PHBTI'-1 and those for PHBTI'-2 in parenthesis.

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF THE RATES OF METAL (M) ION UPTAKE*

Time h	Percentage of the amount of metal ions taken up**		
	Cu ²⁺	Fe ³⁺	UO ₂ ⁺
0.5	38.20 (44.80)	71.20 (76.40)	29.00 (43.20)
1.0	45.70 (59.60)	76.40 (81.30)	58.61 (73.40)
2.0	52.15 (69.63)	87.30 (90.20)	76.53 (89.40)
3.0	59.80 (75.50)	91.20 (93.60)	93.48 (95.90)
4.0	69.40 (85.20)	93.27 (99.30)	96.20 (97.91)
5.0	81.40 (89.50)	98.40 (99.50)	98.66 (99.21)
6.0	89.60 (96.50)	—	—

* [M(NO₃)₂] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (2 ml); [NaNO₃] = 1 mol. dm⁻³ (25 ml); pH 3.0, temp. 32°. Amount of metal ions in the state of equilibrium (100%).

** Notations for PHBTI' same as in Table 4.

ions taken up by a given amount of the polymer samples depends on the nature and concentration of the electrolyte present in the solution. The amounts of Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺ and UO₂⁺ taken up by the polymer samples PHBTI'-1 and PHBTI'-2 increase with the increase in concentration of ions like chloride, perchlorate and nitrate but decrease with the increase in concentration of the sulphate

ions. It was reported¹⁷ that the absorption of Fe^{3+} by salicylic acid-formaldehyde polymer increases with the increase in concentration of chloride, perchlorate and nitrate ions but decreases with the increase in concentration of sulphate and acetate ions. This can be explained on the basis of stability constants of the complexes which are formed with Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} and these polymers.

TABLE 6—DISTRIBUTION RATIOS, *D*, OF DIFFERENT METAL, (*M*) IONS AS FUNCTION OF THE pH

pH	Distribution ratio of the metal ions*		
	Cu^{2+}	Fe^{3+}	UO_2^{2+}
1.3	—	5.31 (6.12)	6.29 (7.65)
1.5	—	143.20 (189.40)	148.60 (179.40)
1.75	—	198.80 (204.60)	199.60 (263.63)
2.0	—	212.60 (256.30)	292.91 (389.00)
2.5	65.90 (71.46)	382.00 (614.30)	399.80 (455.32)
3.0	122.00 (178.20)	—	—
4.0	197.20 (236.20)	—	—
5.0	356.20 (411.67)	—	—
6.0	1212.30 (1823.20)	—	—

* $[\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2] = 0.1 \text{ ml dm}^{-3}$ (2 ml); $[\text{NaNO}_3] = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (25 ml); 32°; 24 h (equilibrium state); notations for PHBTT' same as in Table 4.

The rates of metal adsorption by the PHBTT'-1 and PHBTT'-2 polymers were measured for Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} in presence of NaNO_3 (*M*) to know the time required to reach the stage of equilibrium at pH 3. The results (Table 5) show that UO_2^{2+} and Fe^{3+} required slightly more than four hours for the establishment of equilibrium, while Cu^{2+} required more than six hours. This clearly indicates that the rate of uptake of metal ions follows the order⁹, $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Fe}^{3+} > \text{Cu}^{2+}$. The results in Table 6 reveal that the amount of metal ions taken up by the polymer samples PHBTT'-1 and PHBTT'-2 at equilibrium increases with the increase in pH. The ion exchange study is helpful in selecting the optimum pH for a selective uptake of a particular metal ion from a mixture of different ions. For example, these results suggest the optimum pH 2.5 for the separation of Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} at which the distribution ratio, *D*, of Cu^{2+} for PHBTT'-1 is 71.46 and that of Fe^{3+} is 614.3.

The polymers under study are copolymers and hence it is very difficult to assign their exact structures. Considering the structure of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid-formaldehyde polymers and crosslinked nature of urea or thiourea-formaldehyde homopolymers, the most probable structures for the copolymers suggested are structure I (for PHB : T = 1 : 1) and structure II (for ratio 3 : 1).

(or)

According to the conductometric titration method, it has been observed that the ratio of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and thiourea is approximately equal to 1 : 1 (Table 1) for those polymers which have been prepared from their equimolar proportions. Hence an average molecular weight of repeating unit present in the copolymers (1 : 1 ratio) may be taken as 238 g mol^{-1} by considering the average repeating unit as structure I.

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